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WOMEN'S ALIENATION IN JANE EYRE BY CHARLOTTE BRONTË

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Résumé : Fortement débattue par les écrivains de l'ère victorienne, la « Question de la femme » a constitué l'un des sujets les plus controversés de cette société éponyme. Établi pour garantir un contrôle illégitime des hommes sur les femmes, le système patriarcal leur assurait des rôles actifs, tandis que les femmes se voyaient attribuer des rôles passifs. En tant que femme, Charlotte Brontë a également subi de telles discriminations basées sur le genre, ce qui l'a amenée à critiquer ce système dans *Jane Eyre*, l'une de ses œuvres majeures. Cet article vise donc à examiner l'aliénation des femmes pendant l'ère victorienne. Les mauvais traitements infligés à ces dernières par les hommes et les manifestations de tels traitements inhumains y seront également traités.

Mots Clés : femme, société Victorienne, système patriarcat, discriminations, aliénation des femmes.

Abstract: Strongly debated by Victorian writers, the 'Woman Question' constituted one of the most controversial topics of that eponymous society. Established to ensure men's illegitimate control over women, the patriarchal system promoted active roles for them, whereas women were attributed passive ones. As a woman, Charlotte Brontë was also undergoing such gender discriminations, which led her to criticize this system in one of her prominent works, *Jane Eyre*. Accordingly, this article aims at examining Victorian women's alienation. A stress will be laid on men's mistreatments of women and the psychological manifestations of such inhuman treatments.

Keywords: woman, Victorian society, patriarchal system, discrimination, women's alienation.

Introduction:

Built on Charles Darwin's biological evolution theory, Patriarchy can be defined as a hypothetical system in which the father or the male elder has absolute authority over the family group or over the community as a whole. The victims of that system are mostly female creatures as they undergo violence through gender inequalities.

As a facet of gender disparities, women's alienation is a worth scrutinizing topic because it stands as a referential starting point to present the patriarchal system's arbitrary ideology. This attempt raises the following question: How does Charlotte Brontë treat women's alienation in *Jane Eyre*? To this question, it is hypothesized that she endeavours to denounce it as being an abuse, a form of imprisonment.

Since the publication of her most famous novel *Jane Eyre*, Charlotte Brontë's works have deserved a scholarly attention. Among the most discussed topics was the woman question. A first attempt was to make a distinction between male and female writing in the 1970s. Elaine Showalter's valuable creation of "gynocritics" to qualify studies of such kind, was perceived as a substantial contribution to the critical discourse. Equally significant was Adrienne Rich's publication in *Ms. Magazine* (1973), where the heroine Jane Eyre, outstandingly stood as Rochester's saviour.

Late Twentieth's Feminist works refocused interest in *Jane Eyre* to integrate Bertha Mason in their reflections and review Charlotte Brontë in the large tradition of women novelists. Elaine Showalter's *A Literature of Their Own: British Novelists from Brontë to Lessing* (1977) and Barbara Hill Rigney's *Madness and Sexual Politics in the Feminist Novel: Studies in Brontë, Woolf, Lessing, and Atwood* (1978) are cases in point. Last but not least, inspired by Bertha's madness, Sandra Gilbert and Susan Gubar entitled their remarkable book, *The Madwoman in the Attic: The Woman Writer and the Nineteenth Century Literary Imagination* (1979/2000). The initiative was designed to bring about a deeper understanding of both Emily's and Charlotte's respective works.

The present article aims at showing that patriarchy lies on inequality and exploitation. This is expressed through an illegitimate control over women as it leads to their alienation and destruction. In this respect, both sociological and psychological approaches fit better to our demonstration.

This paper develops four sections. The first analyses Blanche Ingram's submission to the Victorian Ideology. The Second interrogates Bertha Rochester's madness. The third tackles Jane's alienation. The fourth and last develops the double bind of both Jane and Bertha in the novel.

Section I: Blanche Ingram as the ideal Victorian woman

The roles that they were forced to play pushed women to behave in different ways. Some of them manifested their alienation quietly whereas others expressed it violently. It would be appropriate to remind that all the female characters in the novel are alienated by patriarchal domination but we have chosen some of them who

used to express their state of minds more clearly in the Victorian sphere.

Blanche Ingram is among those who accept their condition in society. For her, a woman's life is solely based on seducing a wealthy and virile man who would marry her. That is why she states:

“Oh, I am so sick of the young men of the present day!” exclaimed she, rattling away at the instrument. “Poor, puny things, not fit to stir a step beyond papa’s park gates: nor to go even so far without mama’s permission and guardianship! Creatures so absorbed in care about their pretty faces, and their white hands, and their small feet; as if a man had anything to do with beauty! As if loveliness were not the special prerogative of woman--her legitimate appanage and heritage! I grant an ugly WOMAN is a blot on the fair face of creation; but as to the GENTLEMEN, let them be solicitous to possess only strength and valour: let their motto be:- Hunt, shoot, and fight: the rest is not worth a fillip. Such should be my device, were I a man.” (Brontë, Jane Eyre, 2015, p. 135)

This stance leads us to understand that according to Miss Ingram, beauty must not be men's concern. In other words, men must not waste their time in caring for their faces because it is not their realm. Pulchritude is women's privilege and birth right. Men's maxims are exclusively hunting, shooting, and fighting. In thinking that way, Blanche Ingram is raising a barrier between men's and women's roles and activities in society. In addition, she shows the reader that a woman's role is to polish her appearance so as to seduce men.

Through the activities that Blanche Ingram enumerates, a man's duty, however, is to be active in providing all in the house. He is then the woman's provider and protector. In the same way, Blanche thinking goes deeper when she tells the audience the kind of woman she would be if she ever got married. She puts:

“Whenever I marry,” she continued after a pause which none interrupted, “I am resolved my husband shall not be a rival, but a foil to me. I will suffer no competitor near the throne; I shall exact an undivided homage: his devotions shall not be shared between me and the shape he sees in his mirror. (Jane Eyre, p. 135)

Here, Blanche Ingram lets us bear in mind that if she ever married, she would not contest her husband and would be very respectful to him. He would be the one to have the decision power. It means that Blanche would be submitted to her husband and do whatever he wants her to. Thus, considering all these facts, one can go as far as saying that Blanche Ingram embodies the perfect model of the Victorian woman. In thinking the way she does, Blanche implicitly states women's inferiority.

She also reduces women to objects created to meet men's desires.

Section II: Bertha Rochester's questionable madness

Madness is worth discussing as regards women's alienation in *Jane Eyre*. In effect, Charlotte Brontë presents Bertha Rochester (mostly known through her maiden name as Bertha Mason) as a lunatic. However, it should be remembered that she did not go into that psychological state suddenly. She was surprisingly first declared insane through the eye of her husband Rochester, who placed her in confinement in the third storey of their marital domicile. Most fundamentally, it is only after their honeymoon that Rochester learned that Bertha came from a mad family. Rochester tells us:

My bride's mother I had never seen: I understood she was dead. The honeymoon over, I learned my mistake; she was only mad, and shut up in a lunatic asylum. There was a younger brother, too--a complete dumb idiot. The elder one, whom you have seen (and whom I cannot hate, whilst I abhor all his kindred, because he has some grains of affection in his feeble mind, shown in the continued interest he takes in his wretched sister, and also in a dog-like attachment he once bore me), will probably be in the same state one day. (Jane Eyre, p. 228)

Rochester's sentences prove that he did not really know his new wife. He was not even informed that his mother-in-law was mad. Thus, his wedding with Bertha was a contract. It was an arrangement between the two fathers. Moreover, Rochester suspected that Bertha's brother Richard Mason would also go mad one day. It was according to him the chief characteristic of the family.

Not surprisingly, Bertha's life with Rochester was burdensome as he used to neglect his spouse. The reason for his conduct was cultural: Bertha was not English. Rochester points out Bertha's alien nature when he recounts:

These were vile discoveries; but except for the treachery of concealment, I should have made them no subject of reproach to my wife, even when I found her nature wholly alien to mine, her tastes obnoxious to me, her cast of mind common, low, narrow, and singularly incapable of being led to anything higher, expanded to anything larger--when I found that I could not pass a single evening, nor even a single hour of the day with her in comfort; that kindly conversation could not be sustained between us...when I perceived that I should never have a quiet or settled household, because no servant would bear the continued outbreaks of her violent and unreasonable temper, or the vexations of her absurd, contradictory, exacting orders--even then I

restrained myself: I eschewed upbraiding, I curtailed remonstrance; I tried to devour my repentance and disgust in secret; I repressed the deep antipathy I felt. (Jane Eyre, p. 228)

Without performing his marital role (that of showing affection to his wife), Rochester treated Bertha as a “heterogeneous thing” or an “uncongenial alien” (Shuttleworth, 1996, p. 164). Bertha could not be the wife of an Englishman because Rochester’s expectations had not been satisfied; “*he repeatedly assert[ed] her coarseness...as the central fact of his loathing for her*” (Rich, 1966-1978/1990, p. 150). He had wanted a quiet, tender, and submissive wife, the typical characteristics of a Victorian woman. To his dismay, he realized that he had married the wrong woman, a woman with a different reasoning, a strong character and a different culture of his.

Because Bertha was the kind of women who always expressed what she thought, Rochester began to censure her. He instantly knew that she could not go with his perception of what she should be. He began to find in her defects where they were none. Above and beyond, he convinced himself that he was daily living with a maniac. He gives other overwhelming details concerning Bertha’s state of mind when he describes her as follows:

“Jane, I will not trouble you with abominable details: some strong words shall express what I have to say. I lived with that woman upstairs four years, and before that time she had tried me indeed: her character ripened and developed with frightful rapidity; her vices sprang up fast and rank: they were so strong, only cruelty can check them, and I would not use cruelty. (Jane Eyre, pp. 228-9)

Through this stance, Rochester shows Jane that in previous moments, Bertha had been looking for occasions to fight against him. Bertha became “*a masculine figure which show[ed] ‘virile force’ in [her] contest with Rochester*” (Shuttleworth, p. 166). He realized that as time was passing, she was becoming stronger than he was. Rochester resolved that he could not abuse her physically. Nevertheless, an irreparable harm had already been caused. He had abused her mentally and that was the catalyst for her strange behaviour. Abandoned and neglected by her husband, Bertha began to be filled with a consuming passion that Rochester was incapable to comprehend. As a result, he called for a doctor who declared his wife insane. He placed her into internment, and travelled to seek continental mistresses.

Adrienne Rich describes the situation as follows: “*Once [Bertha] is pronounced mad, he has her locked up, and goes forth on a life of sexual adventures, one result of which has been the child Adèle, daughter of his French mistress*” (p. 150). Indisputably, as any person unjustly locked up, Bertha manifested her anger in a tone of *demon-hate*” (Jane Eyre, p. 230). Through her reaction, Bertha was

expressing her dissatisfaction towards Rochester's action.

In view of the preceding comments, Bertha's attitude that Rochester qualifies as madness was simply the explosion of her passionate nature. Shuttleworth confirms: "*Bertha's insanity is in fact visible proof of her inability to mask her feelings or actions*" (p. 165). Unfortunately, Rochester failed to channel her fierce passion. He failed to distinguish Bertha from his perception of the idyllic woman. Bertha on her part did not succeed in containing her passionate essence in order to conform to the British society's image of the ideal wife.

Section III: Jane Eyre's confinement at Gateshead

At Gateshead, her aunt's house, Jane Eyre happens to be the victim of women's alienation. In fact, after her fight with her cousin John Reed, Jane is immediately sent to the red-room (the place where her uncle died in) by her aunt Mrs Reed. Jane is sent there so that she could calm down her rage. The main purpose of that imprisonment is to force her to learn the rules of society (women's ignorance, passivity, reserve, submission, and stillness).

In the same logic, Mrs Reed tells Jane: "[...] *it is only on condition of perfect submission and stillness that I shall liberate you then*" (*Jane Eyre*, p. 17). Here, Mrs Reed does not suspect that Jane no more wants to be bullied. She is surprised by Jane's attitude. She is confused since Jane has always been conforming to the patriarchal society from her baby state to the age of nine. It is only during her tenth year that she began to change. The reason for Mrs Reed's powerlessness to understand Jane's behaviour lays on the mere fact that she is the representative of the patriarchal authority. She has been raised in that system and has undergone it. Therefore, her mentality has adopted the patriarchal logic. Strikingly, the facts speak for themselves: Jane is alienated by a person of the same gender as hers. It seems to be one of the most dangerous facets of patriarchy seeing that women also serve (willingly or not) as agents to the alienation agenda.

Section IV: Jane and Bertha as psychological doubles

To better understand women's alienation in *Jane Eyre*, let us talk of the double bind of stereotypical female figures expressed by Gilbert and Gubar (1979/2000) in their seminal work entitled the *Madwoman in the Attic*. They support the reasoning according to which male's literary female characters can be categorized as being either "*Angel*" or "*Monster*" (p. 44). The angel character is pure, dispassionate, and submissive, the ideal female character in a male dominated society. The monster on the other hand, is sensual, passionate, rebellious, and uncontrollable. In the novel, Jane Eyre and Bertha Mason are caught by their double psychological personalities. At certain times, Jane has the same qualities as the angel. She is pure, moral, and has a controlled behaviour. However, at other moments, she is passionate, independent, and courageous.

Nevertheless, the double personality of "angel" and "monster" in Bertha

Mason is a little bit difficult to perceive. This difficulty lays on the fact that we know her when she is already mad. Susan Mayer confirms: "*Bertha comes into the novel after about a third of its action has already taken place*" (Meyer, 1996/2007, p. 47). Adrienne Rich corroborates Bertha's brief appearances when she says:

We see little of Bertha Rochester; she is heard and sensed rather than seen. Her presence is revealed by three acts when she escapes into the men-the attempted burning of Mr. Rochester in his bed-chamber, and the stabbing of her brother when he visits Thornfield. The third act is the visit to Jane's bedroom on the night before her wedding and the tearing of the wedding veil. (p. 149)

Because Bertha is confined in the third storey attic, there are no real interactions between her and the other characters in the book. Owing to that imprisonment, one cannot see any angelic side of her. One only has a negative depiction of her by Jane. The latter describes her as having a "*discoloured face*" and "*a savage face*". Bertha is even reduced to a "*Vampyre*" (*Jane Eyre*, p. 212). Thus, these descriptions lead us to think that Bertha is not only bestial and uncivilized, but also monstrous.

Interestingly, to do Bertha Mason justice, Jean Rhys (1966) wrote *Wide Sargasso Sea*. Hers was a prequel, not a pastiche of *Jane Eyre* as Miss Rhys attempted to reveal the circumstances which led Antoinette Cosway (the heroine) to madness. The reason for such an initiative, Francis Wyndham reveals, accounts for the fact that "*For many years, Jean Rhys has been haunted by the figure of the first Mrs. Rochester-the mad wife in Jane Eyre*" (Rhys, 1982, p. 11). The novel is a three-part- one, narrated at first by Antoinette. The second presents Rochester's arrival in the West Indies, and his disastrous marriage as well. The third part, which is now taking place in England, is narrated from Thornfield's third storey attic by Antoinette. The novel finishes when she dreams that she has set fire to Thornfield and has committed suicide.

Significantly, Charlotte Brontë draws some similarities between Jane and Bertha apart from their behavioural and social status differences. Indeed, Bertha's behaviour in the third storey is quite the same as Jane's in the red-room. They express their passions and rage as regards their respective imprisonments. Therefore, their situations imply that neither of the two characters is full angel or full monster but a mixture of the two.

Seen from this perspective, Bertha is the representation of Jane's repressed passions and Jane, Bertha's sane version. In other words, Bertha represents Jane's psychological double and vice versa. Gilbert and Gubar suggest: "[...] *on a figurative and psychological level it seems suspiciously clear that the specter of Bertha is still another-indeed the most threatening-avatar of Jane. What Bertha now does, for instance, is what Jane wants to do*" (p. 359). Wyatt (1985) substantiates: "*while Bertha demonstrates, Jane articulates the causes of her madness*" (p. 207).

The reasons for their passions lay on the basis that they were alienated in the male dominated society in which they were living without any form of independence.

Conclusion

As a conclusion, women's alienation overtly shows how difficult was women's existence in the Victorian society. Charlotte Brontë has, throughout *Jane Eyre*, endeavoured to demonstrate that in such a male dominated arena, women were inculcated to undergo their suffering without complaining. Silence seemed to be their prevailing wisdom. Those who dared to assert themselves were literally confined to coerce them into submission, leading to the fragmentation of their identity (behaving as both angels and monsters). Equally deplorable, the patriarchal ideology goes further in the alienation process when it transforms some women into its representatives.

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